

ANTHROPONYMS IN THE EPIC “THE BIRTH OF GURUGLI”, WHICH ARE INCLUDED IN THEIR OWN AND ASSIMILATED LAYER

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Abstract. *In this article, the lexical composition of the anthroponyms used in the epic “Go‘ro‘g‘lining tug‘ilishi” is analyzed, that is, to which layer they belong.*

Keywords: *anthroponym, real name, non-real name, common nouns.*

INTRODUCTION

In epic onomastics, human names-names placed on heroes-that is, a complex of anthroponyms form a separate group. These names, in turn, are divided into ethnographically and linguistically distinct groups. It is known that the Uzbek people have been in economic, political, cultural contact with other peoples throughout historical periods. These connections have a certain influence on the language of the people with whom they interact. Change and development in the language will be strong in the lexicon of the language. The proverbial names in the onomastics of Uzbek folk epics are genetically grouped according to which language they actually come from. The anthroponyms in the lexicon of the epic “The Birth of the Rainbow”, which we aim to analyze, are also divided into the following groups according to which layer they belong to: the proverbial names in the onomastics of Uzbek folk epics are genetically grouped according to which language they actually come from. The anthroponyms in the lexicon of the epic “The Birth of the Rainbow”, which we aim to analyze, are also divided into the following groups according to which layer they belong:

1. Anthroponyms included in their own layer as applied in the epic.

2. Anthroponyms that are part of the absorption layer used in the epic.

In the epic we witness the use of names belonging to the following languages: Arabic, Persian, Tajik, Uzbek and other languages. And below we will get acquainted with the analysis of anthroponyms in the epic on which vocabulary layer to enter.

Anthroponyms included in their own layer as applied in the epic.

The names of this species are pure Turkic (Uzbek) names. For example:

His wife had a child. His name was Qungirbay.[4:60]

The word **Qungirbay** is a diminutive form of the name of a brown-haired or brown-eyed child or Bell(Snow).

Since the birth of the Gurugli, the lamp has been burning in the cave.[4:60]

Gurugli is exactly: a child born in cave. This name is admired by giving a ratio to the name of the hero of the Uzbek folk epics, Gurugli. In the ancient Turkic language, gor-kor-botir means brave, pahlavon.

Anthroponyms that are part of the absorption layer used in the epic.

Names of this type are anthroponyms derived from Arabic, Persian and Greek, which have entered our language from other languages. For example:

*** Anthroponyms borrowed from Arabic:**

Burungi zamonda Yovmit degan el, Mari degan yana bir qo‘rg‘on bor edi. Yovmit yurtining Odilxon degan podshosi bor edi.[4:3]

The name **Odilkhan**, borrowed from the Arabic lexicon, means a truthful, just, dishonest person. [3:307]

- *Come find out who is the army that comes from!- he sent his chief of Army, Taka begi Zamin, as an emissary, joining the people of birnecha.* [4:7]

A worthy and beloved respected child of **Zamon**. [3:47]

King **Shahdurkhan** the king let it all go. But the Prince had a man named **Hamza**. [4:9]

Hamza is the name of a sharp, bitter, laughing, burning, lamp or medicinal plant. The name is derived from Muhammad (s.a.v.) was the name of his uncle. [5:504]

Shirvan had a king named Rayhon arab. The country of Iraq, Arabia, was a decision; basil fell in love with the arab Khaljuvan. [4:116]

Rayhon is an Arabic name meaning noble, rayhon, or figurative: children mean children. [6:345]

Then a lion, lying in the churchyard, was thrown towards the child. Then Hazrat Khizr came and hit a slap at the lion. [4: 63]

The meaning of the name **Khizr** is green, Khizr is a symbol of eternal vitality, prosperity, good luck. According to the legend, the name of the legendary prophet who found and drank the fountain of the water of life. For this, it is always considered a blessing. He is regarded as a benefactor, a benefactor to the astray. Khidir also has the meanings of pure, pure, veiled (masked).

*Mansur-built dormidi with Anal,
Alive separated, one-eyed zormidi,
Walk, my lamp, says it does not put me,
You brother, did I have an uncle?* [4:66]

The word **Mansur** means pillar, conqueror.

* **Anthroponym borrowed from Persian-Tajik:**

Rustam: -Now I have a state, there will be no sira if I do not have a wife, - took the sister of Badgir. [4:60]

The name of the **Badgir** is the one who turns the right thing , the sentence upside down; yes , the one who does the gina, the one who keeps the gina; the cupcake.

Badkir tilla approached Goorogluni, saying that he would take a lover from soqqa in his hands and deceive and capture Gooroglu. [4:76]

Badkir low hand. Evil evil, despicable; means a person who does such things.

Odilkhan had two sons of the Tsar, The eldest was Uraykhan, and the youngest was Ahmadbek. [4:3]

Uraykhan - anthroponym is considered in the Tajik language and means such meanings as punching, punching, pushing through a hand or something.

Taka Turkman deganyana had a land. In this land, there was a bek boreddi named Zhigalikhan, a son of Zhigalikhan named Gajdumbek, a daughter named Bibi Hilol. [4:4]

Gajdumbek is derived from the root word "gaj", which means curved, bent, crooked in Tajik.

* **Migratory-anthroponyms borrowed from the salbian language.**

But the Prince had a sycamore called Soqim. [4:38]

Soqim-the name expresses the meaning of a lazy, dysfunctional person.

CONCLUSION

In place of the conclusion, we must say that the words belonging to the self and the absorbed layer used in the epic historically have different origins. It should also be noted that many of the anthroponyms used in the epic "The birth of Gurugli" are made up of anthroponyms, mainly those borrowed from Arabic and Persian-Tajik. The meanings they mean also vary. During our

scientific research and research, we will study the names that have mastered and belong to the same layer, as well as subject them to analysis.

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